

Dissecting the binding between glutamine synthetase and its two natively unfolded protein inhibitors[†]

David Pantoja-Uceda^{‡,1,*}, José L. Neira^{#,§,1,*}, Lorena Saelices^{||,¶}, Rocío Robles-Rengel^{||},
Francisco J. Florencio^{||}, M. Isabel Muro-Pastor^{||} and Jorge Santoro[‡]

[‡]*Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano (IQFR), CSIC, Madrid;* [#]*Instituto de Biología Molecular y Celular, Universidad Miguel Hernández, Elche (Alicante);* [§]*Instituto de Biocomputación y Física de Sistemas Complejos (BIFI), Unidad Asociada IQFR-CSIC-BIFI, Universidad de Zaragoza, Zaragoza;*
^{||}*Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, CSIC-Universidad de Sevilla, Seville, Spain.*

Short title: Binding of GS to IFs

¹These two authors contributed equally to this work.

[¶]Current address: Department of Biological Chemistry, and Molecular Biology Institute, University of California, Los Angeles, Los Angeles CA 90095-1570, USA

*Corresponding authors' addresses: David Pantoja-Uceda, Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano, CSIC, 28006 Madrid, Spain. Tel: + 34 917459500. Email: dpantoja@iqfr.csic.es. José L. Neira, Instituto de Biología Molecular y Celular, Universidad Miguel Hernández, Avda. del Ferrocarril s/n, 03202 Elche (Alicante), Spain. Tel: + 34 966658459. E-mail: jlneira@umh.es.

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Abbreviations used: BLI, biolayer interferometry; CD, circular dichroism; DSS 4,4-dimethyl-4-silapentane-1-sulfonic acid; GOGAT, glutamate synthase; GS, glutamine synthetase; IDP, intrinsically disordered protein; IF, inactivating factor; IF7, the *Synechocystis* sp PCC 6803 65-residue-long IF of GS; IF17, the *Synechocystis* sp PCC 6803 149-residue-long IF of GS; K_D , dissociation constant; k_{on} , association rate constant of the binding reactions of IFs to GS; k_{off} , dissociation rate constant of the binding reactions of IFs to GS; NMR, nuclear magnetic resonance; SSP, secondary structure propensity; TFE, 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol.

ABSTRACT

Ammonium is incorporated into carbon skeletons by the sequential action of glutamine synthetase (GS) and glutamate synthase (GOGAT) in cyanobacteria. The activity of *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803 GS type I is controlled by protein-protein interactions with two intrinsically disordered inactivating factors (IFs): the 65-residue-long (IF7) and the 149-residue-long (IF17). In this work, we studied both the IF7 and IF17 by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), and we described their binding to GS, by using NMR and biolayer interferometry (BLI). We assigned the backbone nuclei of all residues of IF7. Analysis of chemical shifts and the $^{15}\text{N}\{-^1\text{H}\}$ -NOEs at two field strengths suggest that IF7 region Thr3-Arg13, and a few residues around Ser27 and Phe41 populated helical conformations (although the percentage is smaller around Phe41). The 2D $^1\text{H}\text{-}^{15}\text{N}$ HSQC and CON experiments suggest that IF17 populated several conformations. We followed the binding between GS and IF7 by NMR at physiological pH, and the residues interacting firstly with IF7 were Gly34, Lys39 and Phe41 (and/or Trp42), close to those regions that appeared ordered. We also determined the k_{on} s and k_{off} s for the binding reactions to GS of both IF7 and IF17, where the GS protein was bound to a biosensor. The measurements of the kinetic constants for the binding reaction of IF7 to GS suggest that: (i) binding

does not follow a kinetic two-state model ($GS + IF7 \xrightleftharpoons[k_{\text{off}}]{k_{\text{on}}[IF7]} GS : IF7$); (ii) there is a strong

electrostatic component in the apparent k_{on} ; and, (iii) the binding is not diffusion-limited.

Assimilation of ammonium is the process by which nitrogen is incorporated into carbon skeletons. This process takes place in the majority of microorganisms by the sequential action of glutamine synthetase (GS) and glutamate synthase (GOGAT). GS is capable of catalyzing the ATP-dependent amidation of glutamic acid to yield glutamine. Then, GOGAT is able to transfer the amide group from glutamine to 2-oxoglutarate yielding two molecules of glutamic acid. This protein network (the so-called GS-GOGAT cycle) is therefore the connecting step between carbon and nitrogen metabolism^{1,2}.

In cyanobacteria, GS type I is modulated at the transcriptional and posttranscriptional levels, according to the nitrogen and carbon supplies³. The classical feedback inhibition, adenylation/deadenylation of GS, observed in other bacteria⁴, does not occur in cyanobacteria. However, there is a posttranslational regulatory mechanism involving protein-protein interactions with a 65-residue-long (IF7) and a 149-residue-long (IF17) inactivating proteins⁵⁻⁷. Analyses of mutant strains devoid of IF7, IF17 or both proteins have shown that each of these contribute to GS inactivation *in vivo*. A maximal level of inactivation *in vitro* has been observed when both proteins are present, although the presence of either of the two, without additional modifications, is enough for GS inactivation⁵. In the presence of ammonium, IF7 and IF17 are expressed and GS is inactivated; on the other hand, removal of ammonium leads to a degradation of IF7 and IF17⁸. The expression of both IFs is modulated by NtcA, the main factor responsible for nitrogen control in cyanobacteria^{3,9,10}.

We have shown that isolated IF7 and IF17 from *Synechocystis* sp PCC 6803 are both intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs)^{11,12}, with no interaction between them¹². In general, IDPs have crucial roles in processes such as cell-cycle control, cellular signalling and transcription¹³. IDPs do not fold in a well-defined globular three-dimensional structure, rather they adopt an ensemble of

rapidly inter-converting conformations, which often, but not always, acquire an ordered structure upon binding to their targets. Among the advantages conferred by disorder are specificity, without excessive binding strength and binding promiscuity^{13,14}. Moreover, it is frequently stated that the most important advantage of intrinsic disorder is the potential for higher association rates (the so-called k_{on} s) of the IDP with its different partners¹⁴. However, recent reports have suggested that there is no experimental evidence to support that IDPs fold faster than their folded counterparts¹⁵⁻¹⁸. In fact, the reported k_{on} s span many orders of magnitude for both disordered and folded proteins, with no statistically difference between both groups of biomolecules¹⁷, and thus, it seems that the k_{on} s reveal distinct, particular features of the IDPs involved in binding¹⁸.

In this work, we describe the conformational preferences of IF7 at atomic level by using NMR techniques. The assignment of its backbone nuclei and the measurement of the $^{15}\text{N}\{-^1\text{H}\}$ -NOEs allowed us to determine which regions of the protein have an intrinsic tendency to become folded. The first half of the protein seems to populate helical conformations between residues Thr3-Arg13, but there is also evidence of folded conformations around residues Met25-Ala29 and Phe41-Thr43. Furthermore, the assignment allowed us to follow which residues interacted firstly with GS: Gly34, Lys39 and Phe41 (and/or Trp42), close to those regions that appeared partially ordered. The NMR experiments with IF17 suggested that the protein had segments with different mobility and several conformations in solution. We also determined the k_{on} s and k_{off} s for the binding reactions to GS of both IF7 and IF17 by biolayer interferometry (BLI), where the GS protein was bound to a biosensor. The use of low urea concentrations in IF17 hampered any reliable conclusion on the kinetics mechanism of the binding reaction. Our results with IF7 suggest that: (i) the binding of IF7 to GS is more complicated than the simplest kinetics two-state model; (ii) the apparent k_{on} has an important electrostatic component; and, (iii) the binding is not diffusion-limited, that is, the k_{on} is smaller than the usual value of $10^5\text{-}10^6\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ s}^{-1}$ of the diffusion-controlled macromolecular interactions¹⁹.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials: Deuterium oxide, deuterated TFE and non-deuterated TFE were obtained from Apollo Scientific (Stockport, UK). The sodium trimethylsilyl [2,2,3,3-²H₄] propionate, TSP, (used for indirect calibration in the 500 MHz magnet) and 4,4-dimethyl-4-silapentane-1-sulfonic acid, DSS, (used for indirect calibration in the 800 MHz magnet) were from Sigma (St. Louis, MO). Ultrapure urea was from MP Biomedicals (USA). Thrombin was purchased from GE (Healthcare, Spain). Dialysis tubing, with a molecular weight cut-off of 3500 Da, was from Spectrapor (Spectrum Laboratories, Japan). Amicon centrifugal devices with a molecular weight cut-off of 3500 Da were from Millipore (Millipore, MA). Standard suppliers were used for all other chemicals. Water was deionized and purified on a Millipore system.

Protein expression and purification: The recombinant GS, IF17 and IF7 proteins were expressed and purified as described by using His-tagged vectors^{5,7,11,12}. Protein stocks were run in SDS-PAGE gels and found to be > 97% pure. The stock of IF17 contained 0.3 M urea, since otherwise IF17 was not soluble. Protein concentrations were determined from the absorbance of individual amino acids²⁰.

For the experiments in BLI, the His-tags of IF7 and IF17 were removed by using thrombin in the proper buffer (20 mM Tris, pH 8.4, 150 mM NaCl and 2.5 mM CaCl₂, which was supplemented with 0.3 M urea in the case of IF17). An amount of 3.5 units of thrombin per mg of protein was added for each protein and the resulting solution was incubated overnight at room temperature. Thrombin was separated from the cleavage reaction by using a Hi-trap benzamidine (GE Healthcare Spain) coupled to an AKTA-FPLC (GE Healthcare), following the absorbance at 280 nm.

NMR spectroscopy: The NMR data were acquired on a Bruker Avance DRX-500 (Bruker GmbH, Germany) spectrometer equipped with a triple-resonance probe and z-gradients, and on a

Bruker AV 800 (Bruker GmbH, Germany) spectrometer equipped with an inverse triple-resonance TCI cryoprobe and z-gradients.

For the sequence-specific assignment of IF7, 1.7 mM of an uniformly ^{13}C - and ^{15}N -labelled sample in 10 mM acetic/acetate buffer, pH 4.5, and 9:1 $\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{D}_2\text{O}$ was used in the Bruker AV 800 at 25 °C. The assignment was obtained by the combination of standard triple resonance techniques²¹ using 2D ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC and 3D HNC(O), HN(CA)CO, intra-HNCA, HN(CO)CA, intra-HNCACB, CBCA(CO)NH and HBHA(CO)NH spectra, and ^{13}C detected methods using 2D CON, 3D (H)N(COCA)NCO and (HN)CO(CA)NCO spectra²². In addition, 2D experiments that provide amino acid type identification of the NH correlation signals of the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum were used to facilitate the assignment process^{23,24}. The triple resonance experiments were acquired with 1 K complex points in the ^1H dimension, 24 complex points in the ^{15}N dimension and 45 or 50 complex points in the ^{13}C dimension, and 4 or 8 scans. The 3D ^{13}C detected spectra were acquired with 512 complex points in the ^{13}CO dimension and 28 complex points in either the ^{15}N or ^{13}CO dimensions, with 4 scans in all cases. The resulting matrix was zero-filled to double the number of original points in all dimensions and shifted squared sine-bell apodization functions were applied in all dimensions prior to Fourier transformation. The programs NMRPipe²⁵ and NMRView²⁶ were used for spectral processing and data analysis, respectively. ^1H chemical shifts were directly referenced to DSS. To avoid any interaction with our protein we used a 3 mm NMR tube filled with our protein sample; we put this tube inside the 5 mm NMR tube filled with DSS. Assignments were referenced in the three dimensions as described²⁷; the BMRB (Biological Magnetic Resonance Bank) accession number for the assignment of IF7 is 25921.

We also tried to assign the 149-residue-long IF7 in the presence of 0.3 M urea at pH 4.5 and 25 °C, at a concentration of 1.6 mM in the Bruker AV 800. However, the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC, even under these conditions, had a smaller number of resonances than expected and even many of those present had different broadening, thus suggesting the presence of several populations within the NMR

timescale. We acquired a CON experiment and a similar broadening to that observed in the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum among the signals was observed (Supplementary Material Fig. 1).

The $^{15}\text{N}\{-^1\text{H}\}$ NOEs of IF7 were measured at both magnetic fields at 25 °C by recording interleaved spectra with and without proton saturation; proton saturation was achieved by a series of 120° pulses, separated by 5 ms delays. The spectra recorded in the presence of proton saturation were acquired with a saturation time of 10 s. The spectra recorded without proton saturation incorporated a relaxation delay of 10 s. At 500 MHz, the number of complex data points in the ^1H dimension was 1 K and those in the ^{15}N one was 100; the number of scans was 128. The experimental set was the same as that in the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC experiments (see below). At 800 MHz, the number of complex data points in the ^1H dimension was 1 K and 64 complex points in the ^{15}N one, with 4 scans. The carrier in the ^1H dimension was set at the water frequency and that of the ^{15}N at 119.636 ppm. The spectral widths used were 12 and 12.8 ppm in the ^1H and ^{15}N dimensions respectively. The NOE ratio was defined as: $\text{NOE} = I_{\text{sat}}/I_{\text{ref}}$, where I_{sat} is the intensity of the corresponding cross peak in the saturated spectrum and I_{ref} is that in the reference (non saturated) spectrum. Peak intensities in the 500 MHz were measured with XWIN-NMR software (Bruker) working on a PC computer and using NMRView²⁶ program in the 800 MHz. Protein concentrations were the same in both magnets. We calculated at each magnetic field the average and the standard deviation of all NOEs by removing those of the last two residues at the C terminus; those averages and standard deviations will be used as cut-off to elucidate the more rigid residues at each field.

Experiments to determine the residues of IF7 titrating upon addition of GS were also carried out in the Bruker Avance DRX-500 at 20 °C, in the presence of 50 mM Tris, pH 7.0. Resonance assignment was extrapolated from pH 4.5: we decided to use pH 7.0 because at acidic pHs GS precipitated¹¹, and the temperature was decreased to diminish solvent-exchange of the remaining amide protons. IF7 concentration was 130 μM , and the final GS concentrations were 2.6, 5.2 and 80 μM . Each concentration of GS was prepared as a fresh new sample with the same amount (130 μM)

of IF7. The titrations were followed by ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC experiments. These were acquired with spectral widths of 30 ppm in the ^{15}N dimension, and 12 ppm in the ^1H one; carrier frequency was set to 120 ppm (for ^{15}N) and 4.7 ppm (water frequency for ^1H). Spectra were acquired in the echo-antiecho mode. The number of complex data points in the ^1H dimension was 1 K and those in the ^{15}N one was 100; the number of scans was 128.

The ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum at pH 4.5 in the presence of 60 % TFE was acquired at 25 °C with 1.6 mM of IF7 in the Bruker Avance DRX-500. The experimental set was the same as that used for the titration with GS, except that 32 scans were acquired *per* experiment.

Biolayer interferometry (BLI): The association (k_{on}) and dissociation (k_{off}) rate constants of the binding reactions of IF7 and IF17 to GS were determined by BioLayer Interferometry using a BLItz system (ForteBio, Pall, Spain)²⁸. The GS (at 1.3 μM) was immobilized on His-tag biosensors (Forte Bio) previously hydrated with 10 x kinetics sample buffer (ForteBio, the 10 X kinetics sample buffer as supplied by the manufacturer was: PBS 1 x, pH 7.4, 10 mM phosphate; 150 mM NaCl; Tween 20 (0.02 %); albumin (0.1 %); and sodium azide (0.05 %)). For the experiments with IF7 in the absence of NaCl, increasing amounts of protein (typically, 0; 0.1; 1; 3; 5 and 10 μM) were used in the association steps. Usually, five to six sensors were used to record the kinetic titration series. For the experiments in the presence of NaCl, an additional concentration of 0.3 M (and then, a final concentration of 0.450 M) was added. The experiments with IF17 were carried out at the similar protein concentrations described above for IF7 in the presence of 0.3 M urea concentration to avoid protein precipitation.

The sensorgrams were in all cases referenced against the buffer reference signal, which was monitored at the beginning of each experiment. The general scheme of the GS-association/dissociation reactions for both proteins was: 30 s of initial baseline with the 10 x kinetics buffer; 120 seconds of loading GS into the biosensor; 30 s of baseline with the 10 x kinetics buffer; 120 seconds of association of either IF7 or IF17 to the biosensor (which had been previously loaded

with GS); and 120 seconds of dissociation from the biosensor of either IF7 or IF17. Similar results to those described (see Results section) were obtained with 300 s of the association step. Base line reference, curve fitting of the sensorgrams and K_D calculation were carried out with the BLItz Pro 1.2 software. The sensorgrams were fit to global and local analysis; in all cases, there were not large differences between both fittings (less than 10 %), and then, the global fittings were used in all cases. The reported errors for the rate constants are fitting errors. The global χ^2 was always less than 0.5 units. Additional fittings were carried out by using Kaleidagraph working on a PC.

Circular dichroism (CD): Far-UV CD measurements of IF7 at different TFE concentrations (from 0 to 60 % (vol/vol)) were carried out on a Jasco J-815 spectro-polarimeter (Jasco, Japan) controlled with a Peltier at 25 °C. The cell path was 0.1 cm. CD spectra were recorded at standard sensitivity, with 50 nm/min scanning speed, 2 s response time, 0.2 nm data pitch and a 1 nm bandwidth. All spectra were the average of 6 scans. IF7 concentration was 20 μ M in 10 mM acetate buffer (pH 4.5). Blank corrections were made in all spectra. The TFE titration was repeated twice with a fresh new sample.

For the thermal denaturation experiments in 60 % TFE, ellipticity at 222 nm was recorded as temperature was increased at a scan rate of 1 °C/min from 25 to 85 °C. Acquisition parameters were: 1 nm of bandwidth, 8 s of response time and 0.2 °C data pitch. Experiments were carried with 20 μ M of protein. The thermal denaturation was repeated twice with a fresh new sample.

Fluorescence: Measurements of IF7 at different TFE concentrations (from 0 to 80 % (vol/vol)) were carried out on a Cary Varian spectrofluorimeter (Agilent, USA), interfaced with a Peltier temperature controller, at 25 °C. Protein concentrations were 5 μ M. Protein samples were excited at 280 and 295 nm in 10 mM acetate buffer (pH 4.5). The slit widths were equal to 5 nm for the excitation and emission lights. Fluorescence spectra were recorded between 300 and 400 nm. The increment of wavelength was set to 1 nm. Blank corrections were made in all spectra. The TFE titration was repeated twice with a fresh new sample.

RESULTS

IF7 and its conformational features

We carried out the backbone assignment of IF7 by using NMR techniques developed for IDPs, since the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum showed signals with similar broadness and enough dispersion (Fig. 1). The use of those assignments in $\delta 2\text{D}$ software²⁹ (www-mvsoftware.ch.cam.ac.uk) yields a prediction of helical populations (larger than 10 %) between residues Gln4 to Arg13, Met25 to Ala29 and Phe41 to Thr43, whereas the rest of the protein seems to populate random-coil conformations (Fig. 2 middle). In total, the $\delta 2\text{D}$ prediction suggests that 29 % of the residues in IF7 adopt helical conformations (helical percentages larger than 10 %) and a 71 % of them populate random-coil conformations. Use of s2D, whose predictions rely only on the protein sequence³⁰, indicates that IF7 has a higher percentage of residues (88 %) populating helical conformations (percentages of helix larger than 10 %) (Fig. 2 bottom). However, in both predictions, the polypeptide regions with the highest percentages of helical conformation correspond to residues around Ala9 and Ser27.

The ^{15}N - $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NOEs measured in IF7 showed very low values at 500 MHz and most of them were negative, suggesting that the protein was not ordered (Fig. 2 top, black line). Only regions Ala9-His14, around residue Leu26, and around Asp40 had values above 0.06 (the average was -0.03 ± 0.09); these polypeptide regions are within those predicted by $\delta 2\text{D}$ and s2D to acquire some ordered structure. Measurements at 800 MHz (Fig. 2 top, grey line) were positive and showed also two regions with the highest values (above 0.44, the average was 0.34 ± 0.10) around Ala9 and Asp40. Comparison between the results at both fields suggests that the NOE profile was flatter at 800 MHz, as it has been observed in other IDPs³¹.

Thus, taken together the analysis of chemical shifts, the analysis of the primary sequence and the NOE data, we suggest that the polypeptide regions of IF7 around Leu10 and Phe41 have an intrinsic tendency to populate helix-like conformations.

Since there is an intrinsic tendency to acquire helical conformations at the N terminus of IF7, we reasoned that the use of TFE could help to stabilize such populations. The 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol (TFE) is known for stabilizing pre-formed or marginally stable α -helices by mimicking the hydrophobic environment experienced by proteins in protein-protein interactions or within the tertiary structure of a protein³². To that end, we carried out TFE titrations by using fluorescence and far-UV CD. The fluorescence spectrum of isolated IF7 in aqueous solution has a maximum wavelength at ~ 350 nm¹¹. As the concentration of TFE increased, there was a decrease in the spectrum intensity with a shift in the maximum towards blue-wavelengths (Supplementary Material Fig. 2 A, main panel). However, there was not a sigmoidal tendency in the fluorescence intensity at any of the explored wavelengths (Supplementary Material, Fig. 2 A, inset). The far-UV CD of isolated IF7 has been also described before: it resembles that of an unfolded polypeptide chain, with a shoulder at 222 nm¹¹. As the concentration of TFE was raised the absolute value of the raw ellipticity increased suggesting the acquisition of helical-like structure (Supplementary Material, Fig. 2 B, main panel). In contrast to that observed by fluorescence intensity, the ellipticity at 222 nm followed a sigmoidal behaviour (Supplementary Material, Figure 2 B, inset), with absence of native baseline at low concentrations of TFE. The highest ellipticity and, therefore, the highest population of helical structure, was observed at 60 % TFE. These results prompted us to acquire: (i) a far-UV CD thermal denaturation at 60 % TFE to show the melting of the helical structure; and, (ii) a ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum at 60 % TFE to elucidate whether there was a spreading of amide cross-peaks under these conditions. The absence of sigmoidal behaviour in the thermal denaturation indicates that the helix-like structure suggested by far UV CD spectra is not rigid (Supplementary Material, Fig. 3 A). Moreover, the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum did not show a spreading of the resonances (Supplementary

Material, Fig. 3 B), and was similar to the spectrum of an isolated IDP protein in aqueous solution. These results suggest that the structure acquired at 60 % TFE was not stable.

We also tried to assign IF17 in the presence of 0.3 M urea, but the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC and the CON spectra showed a smaller number of signals than could be expected (Supplementary Material, Fig. 1). Furthermore, the intensity among the signals changed drastically suggesting that the protein had a sort of conformational-exchange equilibrium comprising several polypeptide patches. These unfavourable features hampered the assignment. As IF7 has a high sequence similarity with the C-terminal region of IF17¹², in the absence of an assignment of IF17, we hypothesize that its C-terminal region also has a higher helical propensity than the rest of its polypeptide chain.

Residues of IF7 involved in binding to GS

Since GS precipitates at low pH¹¹, we carried out the NMR titration between GS and IF7 at pH 7.0. At this pH, the number of observable signals of IF7 decreased dramatically (when compared to that at pH 4.5), because most of the amide protons are not hydrogen-bonded and they are not protected from solvent exchange due to its highly flexible nature (Fig. 3, middle spectrum, compare with the left one at pH 4.5). The only amide protons observed at this pH (apart from the side-chains of Asn and Gln) were Leu10, Met11, Arg13 (and/or Ile33), Leu26 (and/or Ala31), Ala29 (and/or Ala37), Ala30, Glu32, Gly34, Val35, Glu36, Glu38, Lys39, Asp40, Phe41 (and/or Trp42), Thr43 and Ser65. Many of these residues are close to, or are, an acidic residue, and thus, they could be hydrogen-bonded with the side-chain, and therefore protected from exchange with the solvent; the others have a bulky side chain, which could also hamper solvent-accessibility. In fact, it has been known for a long time that hydrogen-bonding and burial from solvent are the main reasons behind solvent-protection³³. It is interesting to note that most of the residues observed at pH 7.0 were those with the largest NOEs (see above), or predicted to populate helix-like conformations (Fig. 2), where the amide protons can be hydrogen-bonded (and thus solvent-protected) part of the time.

The binding of GS to IF7 was characterized using NMR chemical shift perturbations in 2D ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectra of the above remaining signals. At this stage, it is interesting to note that holo and apo GS molecules are invisible to solution-state NMR due to its large size (GS is formed by 12 subunits of approximately 50 kDa organized in two hexameric rings³⁴). Thus, the residues of IF7 important for binding to GS can be observed only when the exchange between the fully-bound IF7 and the free-state IF7 is sufficiently fast, and otherwise, they will disappear upon binding to GS. In addition, the strength of the changes in the cross-peaks of IF7 will depend on: (i) the conformation and chemical environments for each particular residue; and (ii) the concentration of the bound species. Upon addition of 2.6 μM GS to the solution, the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum showed the disappearance of signals of Gly34, Lys39 and Phe41 (or Trp42, which overlapped). The ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC at 5.2 μM of GS showed, in addition, the disappearance of Asp40. The non-uniform broadening (and then, the disappearance of peaks) is caused by an exchange of IF7 molecules between their free and their GS-bound state that is intermediate within the NMR time scale. The ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum at the highest concentration of GS (80 μM) (Fig. 3, right side) showed only the cross-peak of Ser65 (apart from the side chains of Asn and Gln). Thus, the residues interacting firstly with GS are those with a positively charged side-chain (Lys39), those with an aromatic residue (Phe41 and/or Trp42) and Gly34, and all of them are close to, or involved in, the polypeptide patches that are predicted to acquire helical structure. These findings are also in agreement with previous fluorescence results from our groups, since the affinity constant of IF7 for GS could be determined by changes in fluorescence of the sole tryptophan (Trp42)¹¹; accordingly, the NMR results in this work indicate that one of the first residues affected by the presence of GS is Phe41 and/or Trp42.

The kinetic parameters of the binding reaction of IF7 to GS

Since IF7 is an IDP, we were also interested in elucidating which are the rate constants of the binding reaction to GS to compare the values with those reported in the literature for other IDPs¹⁷. The k_{on} was $(3.2 \pm 0.2) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the k_{off} was $(3.03 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ both in 150 mM NaCl

(the amount contained in the kinetic buffer) (Fig. 4 a). The rate of both constants, assuming a 1:1 kinetic model for the GS-IF7 binding, yields a K_D of $0.9 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$, which is within the same order of magnitude than that obtained by equilibrium fluorescence titrations: $0.3 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{M}^{11}$. In the presence of 450 mM of NaCl, the k_{on} was $(2.46 \pm 0.09) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (smaller than that measured at low concentrations of NaCl) and the k_{off} was $(2.75 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (similar to that measured at low concentrations of NaCl); these values result in a K_D of $1.1 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{M}$, identical within the error, to that determined by kinetics at low NaCl concentrations. Thus, it seems that the affinity was not altered by the presence of a high ionic strength.

The difference between the value of K_D measured by fluorescence and that determined by the rate of the kinetic constants prompted us to calculate the K_D from the values of R_{eq} at the different concentrations of IF7. The R_{eq} is defined as the signal in the sensorgram at infinite time in the kinetic association experiment, that is, when the association equilibrium is reached; this analysis provides a strictly thermodynamic approach to determine the equilibrium K_D . If the simple binding model in the kinetic measurements is correct, then R_{eq} should be related to the K_D obtained from the thermodynamic measurements³⁵. The fitting of the R_{eq} values in IF7 yielded a K_D of $0.14 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{M}$ (Fig. 4 b); this figure is similar, within the error, to that from fluorescence measurements ($0.3 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{M}$), but smaller than the value determined from the rate of k_{on} and k_{off} ($0.9 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$, see above). Thus, these results pinpoint that the binding of GS to IF7 does not follow the simplest kinetic two-

discussion to compare with the values measured in other IDPs, where a 1:1 mechanism is proposed.

The kinetic parameters of the binding reaction of IF17 to GS

Although the presence of IF7 is enough to inactivate GS *in vitro*, the presence of IF17 together with IF7, reinforces GS inactivation *in vivo*⁵. We wondered whether the binding reaction of IF17 to

GS had similar association or dissociation rates to that of IF7. However, it is important to bear in mind that the measurements of IF17 were carried in the presence of 0.3 M urea (which affects solution viscosity³⁶) to ensure protein solubility (Fig. 5). We obtained a k_{on} of $(1.75 \pm 0.08) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and a k_{off} of $(2.6 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, smaller than those of IF7. These results yield a K_D of $0.15 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{M}$, which is ten-times smaller than the value of $1 \mu\text{M}$ measured from equilibrium fluorescence titrations¹². Similarly to IF7, this difference suggests that the IF17 binding does not follow a kinetic

DISCUSSION

Kinetic features of the binding of IFs to GS

The association rate constant of two proteins, k_{on} , for a diffusion-limited reaction can be predicted with a simple model^{19,37}. Such approach considers the proteins as two uniformly reactive species, which diffuse freely in solution with an upper k_{on} limit of $10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ³⁸. However, proteins are not uniformly reactive over their entire surface and they must rotate to acquire a correct orientation to collide with the other protein. This rotational diffusion decreases the limit of k_{on} by several orders of magnitude leading to a range of 10^5 - $10^6 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the diffusion-limited reactions³⁹. This value is still larger than the apparent k_{on} measured for the binding between IF7 and GS ($24600 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), indicating that the reaction between both proteins is not diffusion-limited, under our conditions.

The value of the apparent k_{on} of IF7 is, however, within the same order of magnitude than those of other proteins, where one of the partners is also an IDP of similar size to IF7 (less than 100-residues), and measured by biosensor-using technology⁴⁰⁻⁴². This IF7 k_{on} is almost two-fold larger than that of IF17 (17000 versus $24600 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), indicating that, although *in vivo*, the binding of both proteins results in a more efficient inactivation of GS, IF7 is faster than the IF17 to reach its target (and with a slightly larger affinity^{11,12}). Several factors affect the values of k_{on} s: (i) diffusion (smaller in a larger polypeptide chain); (ii) conformational changes in the interacting proteins (in the two IDPs here); and (iii) electrostatic forces (between IFs and GS). Since both IFs are disordered and the sequence of IF17 at its C-terminus is similar to that of IF7¹², the differences in the apparent k_{on} s of both proteins could be due to their chain lengths and the urea concentration used for IF17.

Based on thermodynamic measurements, we have previously suggested that upon binding to GS, IF17 (and probably IF7) becomes folded¹². It has been proposed that due to the conformational changes that occur in IDPs upon binding to their targets, there is a strong relationship between k_{on}

and K_D , measured by thermodynamic means⁴³. In the two IFs, we observed such relationship occurring with the plot of bone morphogenesis protein (Fig. 1B⁴³). Furthermore, we can use this plot to predict the real k_{on} s for both proteins, assuming that the values of the K_D s thermodynamically measured are correct^{11,12}. From that plot, we obtain 17000 and 5600 $M^{-1} s^{-1}$ for IF7 and IF17, respectively, which are smaller than the apparent values obtained from BLI (24600 *versus* 17000 $M^{-1} s^{-1}$). Thus, the folding of both IFs, upon binding to GS, slows down their association rates.

The value of k_{on} in IF7 showed a strong dependence on the concentration of NaCl: it decreased 1.3-times as the concentration of NaCl was increased 2-fold, indicating that the binding is governed by electrostatic interactions. This electrostatic behaviour has been observed in other protein-protein interactions, involving either IDPs or fully ordered proteins^{15,16,39,44}. On the other hand, there was a small decrease in the k_{off} with the increase of the ionic strength (from 3.03 to 2.75 $\times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$), in agreement with previous work with protein-protein complexes³⁹. This is due to the fact that dissociation is mainly dictated by the strength of short-range interactions between the proteins (that is, van der Waals, hydrogen-bonding, hydrophobic interactions and even salt-bridges).

Unfortunately, kinetic mechanisms cannot be proved, instead mechanisms can be only ruled out. Based on the disagreement between the kinetic measurements presented in this work, and the previous thermodynamic measurements¹², we suggest that both IFs do not follow a two-state model

of binding to GS; in other words, the kinetic mechanism is not: $GS + IF \xrightleftharpoons[k_{off}]{k_{on}[IF]} GS : IF$, and in

fact, other IDPs show complex kinetics^{45,46}. Instead, the binding of both IFs to GS might entail: (i) the formation of an intermediate (the species marked with the asterisk), where the folding of the IF is

completed after binding to GS ($GS + IF \xrightleftharpoons[k_{off}]{k_{on}[IF]} GS : IF^* \xrightleftharpoons[k_{off}^*]{k_{on}^*} GS : IF$); or (ii) the pre-selection

of a populated partially folded conformation in the IF pool (IF_{folded}) which is capable of binding to

binding mechanisms is followed by both IFs. These mechanisms are called folding after binding (or induced-fit)⁴⁷, and conformational selection (which is identical to Monod-Wyman-Changeaux model⁴⁸, respectively. In practice, a combination of both mechanisms is also possible⁴⁹, which can be further altered by the concentration of binding (ligand) protein^{47,50}. We are tempted to suggest that, given the high helical SSP of IF7 at its N terminus, the conformational selection mechanism could be prevalent in binding of both IFs to GS⁵¹. This hypothesis is consistent with helical structure formation, which occurs on a μ s time scale⁵², much faster than the association time constant for IF7 ($4.1 \text{ s} = 1/(24600 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M})$). However, the existence of such low-populated, folded conformations in IDPs does not imply that folding-upon-binding occurs through the conformational selection mechanism, as it has been shown in some IDPs^{53,54}. In fact, the mechanism of binding of both IFs to GS, due to their different lengths, non-conserved residues and the additional ones at the N terminus of IF17¹², could be fully different between both species, as it has been shown in other IDPs⁵⁵.

Structure-activity relationships in binding of GS to IF7

We have discussed that the fact that there is a strong dependence of the association kinetics rate with NaCl concentration suggests that ionic interactions intervene in the binding of GS to IF7. We have observed that the residues of IF7 that are firstly involved in the binding to GS were Gly34, Lys39 and Phe41 (and/or Trp42). These residues are, except for Lys39, highly hydrophobic. However, upon a larger addition of GS, Asp40 also was involved in binding. These results suggest that: (i) the kinetic mechanism is not two-state, since different residues bind differently, supporting our kinetic data; and, (ii) binding involves both electrostatic and hydrophobic contacts, also observed in other large protein-protein complexes⁵⁶.

Mutational studies of IF7 have shown that substitution of Arg8, Arg21 and Arg28 by glutamic acid abolishes the ability of the mutant protein to inactivate GS⁵⁷. In addition, molecular modelling of the binding of IF7 to GS with a short fragment of IF7, comprising its first 38 residues, suggests that residues Arg8, Arg21 and Arg28 are involved in binding to GS⁵⁸. We could not observe any of these residues at pH 7.0, since they are highly solvent-exposed (Fig. 3, middle panel), and thus, our NMR experiments could not rule out their importance in the binding to GS. However, two of them belong to the polypeptide region, which has been predicted to adopt helical secondary structure (Fig. 2, middle and bottom panels), and to intervene in binding to GS¹².

We suggest that the formation of GS-IF complexes is characterized by a minimal interface, which from the mutational studies would involve highly charged residues. This minimal interface would serve as an anchor point for the complex formation and its strengthening. This intermediate complex would be fixed at a later step by hydrophobic contacts, as proposed to occur in otherwise complexes of IDPs⁵⁹. Under this hypothesis, the surface of GS would not provide a simple set of constraints that would force the folding of IFs, but rather the surface of GS would act as a facilitator of folding⁶⁰. The facilitation and the environment provided by the hexameric rings of GS are critical for both IFs, since IF7 is not capable of acquiring a well-fixed helix-like structure (low populated when the protein is isolated in solution) even in the presence of the hydrophobic environment granted by TFE.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION AVAILABLE

Figures containing the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC and CON of IF17 (Fig. 1); the fluorescence and CD TFE titration of IF7 at pH 4.5 (Fig. 2); and the structural features of IF7 in the presence of 60 % TFE (Fig. 3). The figures are available free of charge at [http:// www.acs.pub.org](http://www.acs.pub.org).

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FIGURE LEGENDS

FIGURE 1: **^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum of IF7.** The assignment of IF7 is shown for the spectrum of IF7. Signals with an asterisk correspond to folded peaks. Signals with a negative number correspond to residues in the His-tag (with sequence SSGLVPRGSH). Spectrum was acquired in a Bruker AV 800, at pH 4.5 and 25 °C.

FIGURE 2: **Relaxation and sequence analysis of IF7.** (Top) NOE ratios of IF7 at 800 MHz (grey line) and 500 MHz (black line). The dashed lines correspond to values greater than one standard deviation above the average NOE value for each field, removing the last two C-terminal residues. (Middle) Secondary structure propensity (SSP) obtained from d2D software²⁹ using the assignment of IF7. (Bottom) SSP obtained by using s2D software³⁰ and the primary structure of IF7.

FIGURE 3: **Titration of IF7 with GS.** ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectra of isolated IF7 (130 μM) at pH 4.5 (left), 7.0 (middle), and in the presence of 80 μM of GS (right). Spectra were acquired in the Bruker DRX-500 at 20 °C and pH 7.0.

FIGURE 4: **Kinetics of the binding between GS and IF7 as monitored by BLI.** (A) Sensorgrams at the different concentrations of IF7 used (pseudo-first order conditions). The first 150 seconds correspond to the loading of biosensor with GS and equilibration with the buffer. (B) Plot of the steady state response, R_{eq} , versus the IF7 concentration for determination of the binding affinity, K_D . The line through the data is the fitting to a binding 1:1 curve. Temperature was 25 °C.

FIGURE 5: Kinetics of the binding between GS and IF17 as monitored by BLI. Sensorgrams at the different concentrations of IF17 used (pseudo-first order conditions). The first 150 seconds correspond to the loading of biosensor with GS and equilibration with the buffer. Temperature was 25 °C.

Fig. 1 (Pantoja-Uceda et al.)

Fig. 2 (Pantoja-Uceda et al.)

Fig. 3 (Pantoja-Uceda et al.)

Fig. 4 (Pantoja-Uceda et al.)

Fig. 5 (Pantoja-Uceda et al.)

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